

ISic0389

I.Sicily inscription 0389

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

in pascuis Ferrandi Ioenii' (M)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141198

1. MN

2. AR

3. $\hat{V}B$

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491600

EDR 141198

EDCS 21900429

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ,

cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.52-53
Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae
Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus
Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae
Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7107 ([http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/
CILv10pII1883](http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883))

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384387>